
Application of Christian Leadership in Work Motivation Towards Christian Religious Exams

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Article history:

Received: September 12, 2024; Accepted: November 15, 2024; Displayed Online: November 20, 2024; Published: December 30, 2024

Keywords

Leadership;

Work Motivation;

*Religious Extension
Workers;*

Abstract

This study investigates the crucial role of Christian religious extension workers, focusing on their contributions to community guidance and the promotion of Christian values as well as religious moderation. The research aims to highlight the impact of these extension workers on the community and the broader implications of their work. Additionally, the study explores the relationship between Christian leadership and the work motivation of these extension workers. It employs a quantitative methodology. The findings of the research reveal a significant application of Christian leadership principles among extension workers. This is evidenced by the elevated levels of work motivation observed within this group, indicating that effective Christian leadership not only fosters a sense of purpose but also enhances overall job satisfaction and engagement. The results underscore the importance of integrating Christian values into leadership practices, as they play a vital role in motivating extension workers to fulfill their responsibilities and contribute positively to their communities. Overall, the study contributes valuable insights into the dynamics of Christian leadership and its influence on work motivation within the context of religious extension work. By highlighting the positive correlation between these factors, the research emphasizes the need for ongoing support and development of Christian leadership skills among extension workers, ultimately aiming to strengthen their impact on community guidance and the promotion of religious values.

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1. Introduction

Christian leaders, as representatives of God, are called to engage in noble endeavors that reflect their divine mission (Sunquist, 2013). They are tasked with emulating the example set by Jesus Christ in their leadership roles, which requires them to embody humility and serve as role models for their peers. By adhering to the teachings and example of the Lord Jesus Christ, Christian leaders are not only equipped to confront challenges effectively but also to inspire motivation and foster a sense of purpose among their colleagues (Kouzes, J. M., & Posner, 2023). This alignment with Christ's example serves as a guiding principle for their leadership practices, enabling them to navigate complexities with grace and integrity.

A well-structured framework of relationships is a fundamental component of any organization, delineating authority, responsibility, and the division of labor necessary for executing specific functions. In this context, the presence of effective leadership transcends mere desirability; it becomes essential for the success of the organization. When leadership is absent, the alignment between individual aspirations and organizational objectives tends to weaken, which highlights the critical importance of leadership in fostering cohesion and enhancing overall effectiveness. Effective leadership ensures that everyone within the organization is working towards common goals, thereby reinforcing a shared vision and purpose.

Without leadership, an organization risks devolving into a mere collection of individuals and machines, lacking the necessary organization and direction to achieve its goals (Gill & Pitt, 1999). This observation underscores the vital role of leadership in establishing order and facilitating the attainment of objectives. Leadership is paramount, as it embodies the ability to influence others to pursue shared goals with enthusiasm and commitment, thereby transforming potential into reality. In essence, strong leadership not only guides individuals but also cultivates an environment where collective efforts can flourish, ultimately driving the organization toward success.

2. Research Method

This study utilized a quantitative research methodology to systematically explore the subject matter at hand (Gentles et. al., 2016). By adopting this approach, the research aimed to provide a clear, objective analysis of the data collected. The data collection techniques employed in this study included observation, the distribution of structured questionnaires, and the review of pertinent documentation.

The primary instrument for gathering data was a carefully crafted structured questionnaire designed specifically to elicit comprehensive and relevant information from the participants. This instrument was instrumental in ensuring that the data collected was both reliable and valid, allowing for a thorough examination of the research questions.

The participants in this study consisted of Christian religious instructors affiliated with the Ministry of Religion Office in Kupang Regency, Indonesia. The total population included 39 individuals, all of whom were selected based on their relevance to the study's focus, by concentrating on this specific group, the research aimed to capture the unique perspectives and experiences of these instructors, thereby enhancing the depth and quality of the findings.

Overall, the combination of quantitative methods, diverse data collection techniques, and a targeted participant group provides a robust framework for understanding the dynamics of Christian leadership and motivation within the context of the Ministry of Religion. This methodological rigor not only strengthens the credibility of the research outcomes but also lays a solid foundation for future studies in this area.

3. Discussion and Results

A. Christian Leadership

In his book *Everyone Communicates Few Connect* (2010), John C. Maxwell says that to communicate effectively and lead others, you must take the initiative, be proactive, and be more than just surviving. I admit that if I want to be someone who moves forward, leads others, and leads a successful organization, I must be more than just surviving. I need to build relationships.

According to Pickwell, J. L., & Henson (2022), leadership is an example that must be followed and become a role model because followers or the wider community always sees it and is also a process that can influence others to do what is ordered to achieve common goals. Thus, every organization certainly needs a qualified leader, has character, is moral, has the right motivation, and is a role model. As a Christian leader, the leader's personality is very much needed and prioritized.

Therefore, a good leader must have experience in leading, meaning preparing themselves to be a good leader in carrying out their leadership (Kouzes, J. M., & Posner, B. Z., 2024). If it is just leadership theory without experience, then it will not be enough. Becoming a leader does not just happen; it can be developed within a person to become a person with the character of a good leader.

B. Work Motivation

Motivation comes from the Latin word "movere," which means encouragement, driving force, or strength that causes an action or deed (Reeve, 2024). The word "move" in English is often equated with "Motivation," which means giving a motive, giving rise to a motive, or something that causes a drive or a condition that causes a drive. Literally, motivation is understood as giving a motive. Employees work because they have a motive. The motive is related to the intent or goal that they want to achieve. In general, the main motive for employees to work is to seek income, develop their potential, actualization, and the need for appreciation.

In general, there are two types of motivation: internal and external (Legault, L., 2020). Included in the motivation from within a person is the individual's perception of themselves, self-esteem and achievements, hopes for the future, needs, and job satisfaction. While external motivation is the type and nature of work, work groups, general environmental situations, and the reward system received, this arises because of external stimuli from a person. So, the conclusion of work motivation, a power of ability or strength to meet needs, is influenced by motivational factors in increasing a person's ability to carry out their duties. Each person's work motivation is influenced by their spiritual intelligence or devotion to God in carrying out their worship through the world of work.

C. Christian Religious Counselor

Counselor comes from the word "torch," which is an item used to light. Counselor means a provider of light and guidance (McConnell et al., 2020). A Christian religious counselor is a person who provides light and shows the right path within the scope of Christianity. Counselors are essential as the vanguards in the midst of society and the spearheads about ethics, morality, and Christian values in community life.

Religious counselors are guides to religious communities in the context of mental, moral, and devotion to God Almighty development. Religious Counselors are guided to religious communities in

the context of mental and moral development to the One God. Mental development is closely related to the human mind and character, and it can generate motivation within a person.

The leadership of the Lord Jesus, with the concept of serving and not to be served, focuses on human resources with noble morals. Jesus set an example by serving His disciples, including washing their feet, which is the duty of a servant. In Greek, the word "Servant" is δούλος (doulos). This word is often used in the context of describing someone who completely gives himself to serving others, emphasizing loyalty and commitment.

The Lord Jesus explained that Christian leadership is different from worldly leadership, which is leading with an iron fist to exercise his power (Dixon, 2021). While Christian leadership is, a leader in the Kingdom of God is a servant who becomes a servant for others (Matthew 20:25-26). So, servant leadership is about leading with love, serving, and prioritizing the welfare of others above personal interests.

The term servant (Greek 'Diakonos') is used as the most common term for Christian service tasks in the NT, and every "servant" must remember the true meaning of the word. In the Gospel of Mark 10:43-44 is the leadership concept that places followers' interests and needs as the main priority. Some important principles in servant leadership are:

1. Humble and not self-effacing. Servant leaders have a humble nature and do not demand to be praised.
2. Serving followers. Servant leaders focus on serving and meeting the needs of followers, not just giving orders.

4. Research Implementation Results

The research findings stem from a comprehensive data collection process that involved distributing questionnaires to a specific group of respondents, namely the Christian religious counselors working at the Ministry of Religion Office in Kupang Regency. To ensure the relevance and appropriateness of the data collected, the study employed a purposive sampling technique. This method is characterized by selecting samples based on predetermined criteria that align with the objectives of the research.

In this case, the criteria for inclusion were clearly defined to focus solely on Christian religious counselors affiliated with the Ministry of Religion Office in Kupang Regency. The total number of participants in this study amounted to 39 individuals, each of whom met the specified criteria. This targeted approach not only enhances the validity of the findings but also ensures that the insights gathered are directly applicable to the context of Christian leadership and work motivation within this specific group.

By utilizing purposive sampling, the research effectively captures the perspectives and experiences of those who are most relevant to the study's aims. This methodological choice underscores the commitment to obtaining meaningful and actionable data that can inform future practices and policies within the Ministry. Overall, the careful selection of respondents and the structured data collection process contribute significantly to the robustness and credibility of the research outcomes. The sample size was determined using the Slovin formula, namely: $n = \frac{N}{(1+Ne^2)}$

Note:

n = Sample

N = Population

e = The level of error in sampling

The size of the research sample using the Slovin formula approach will be determined by the level of error value, where the greater the level of error used, the smaller the number of samples taken. In this study, the error rate was 1% with a population of 63 people:

$$n = \frac{63}{1+63(0,1)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{63}{1+63(0,01)}$$

$$n = \frac{63}{1+0,63}$$

$$n = \frac{63}{1,63}$$

$$n = 38.65$$

This count can be rounded up to 39 people.

To calculate the value and data analysis, the study used a Likert scale, and each answer was given its own score. The research score for 20 positive questions with 5 alternative answers was SS (Strongly Agree) 5, S (Agree) 4, N (Neutral) 3, TS (Disagree) 2, and STS (Strongly Disagree) 1. The question is to find out the respondents' responses about the Implementation of Christian Leadership on work motivation for Christian Religious Extension Workers at the Ministry of Religion of Kupang Regency. This questionnaire is helpful in obtaining data, which will then be processed. The results of the respondents' answers are then summarized and analyzed with the following formula percentage:

$$P = \frac{F}{N} \times 100\%$$

Note : P = Presentation
F = Frequency
N = Respondent

Variable (X) Implementation of Christian Leadership

Based on the results of distributing a questionnaire on the Implementation of Christian Leadership in Work Motivation for Christian Religious Counselors at the Ministry of Religion Office, Kupang Regency, there were 39 respondents who answered the questionnaire, and the overall results of the data were processed using the formula: $P = \frac{F}{N} \times 100\%$. The following is a summary table of the overall frequency of variable values (X) as follows: Variable (X) Implementation of Christian Leadership Based on the results of distributing a questionnaire on the Implementation of Christian Leadership in Work Motivation for Christian Religious Counselors at the Ministry of Religion Office, Kupang Regency, there were 39 respondents who answered the questionnaire, and the overall results of the data were processed using the formula.

*Overall Frequency Recapitulation of Answer Items
Application of Christian Leadership (X)*

Scores (S)	Frequency (F)	(S) x (F)
5	220	1100
4	157	628
3	12	36
2	1	2
1	0	0
Total	390	1766

From the table above, the known total score For the variable Implementation Christian Leadership (X) is categorized based on the range ideal score where:

1. Maximum score obtained from 5 (Highest score) multiplied by the number of statement items times of respondents, namely $5 \times 10 \times 39 = 1950$
2. Amount minimum score obtained from 1 (Lowest score) multiplied by several question items times the respondents, namely $1 \times 10 \times 39 = 390$.
3. Range score = (Maximum score - Minimum score): 5. With this range score For variable Implementation Christian Leadership (X) = $(1950 - 390) : 5 = 312$.

Based on the research results, 39 respondents provided scores for the variable representing the Implementation of Christian Leadership (X), yielding a total score of 1,766. This score falls within the "high" category. When calculated, this score translates to a percentage of 90.56%, derived from the formula: 1,766 divided by 1,950, which equals 0.9056. Interpreting this value, a score of 0.90 or 90% indicates that it resides within the interval of 0.80 to 1.00, corresponding to a range of 86% to 100%, which reflects a very high level of implementation. Therefore, the result for the Implementation of Christian Leadership (Variable X), with a score of 90.56, is classified as very high, signifying a strong adherence to Christian leadership principles among the respondents. These findings underscore the effectiveness of Christian leadership practices within the surveyed group, suggesting that the respondents exhibit a robust commitment to implementing these principles in their respective roles. This high level of implementation may have significant implications for the overall impact of Christian leadership in their community and organizational settings.

Guidelines Interpretation

Coefficient Interval	Relationship Level
0.00 - 0.19	Very Low
0.20 - 0.39	Low
0.40 - 0.59	Currently
0.60 - 0.79	Tall
0.80 - 0.1.00	Very high

Based on the calculation results presented above, we can confidently conclude that the findings from the questionnaire regarding the implementation of Christian leadership yielded a score of 0.90. This score falls within the interpretative guidelines that classify any result in the range of 0.80 to 1.00 as "very high."

Thus, the score of 0.90 signifies a strong affirmation of the effective implementation of Christian leadership principles among the respondents. This high score indicates that the Christian religious counselors perceive the implementation of Christian leadership within their organization as exceptionally effective and impactful.

Moreover, the overwhelmingly positive response from the counselors highlights their strong endorsement of the leadership practices in place. Such a high level of agreement suggests that the counselors not only recognize the importance of Christian leadership but also feel that it is being successfully integrated into their professional environment.

In summary, the results underscore the critical role that effective Christian leadership plays in shaping the experiences and perceptions of the counselors. The very high score of 0.90 reflects a robust commitment to and appreciation for the implementation of Christian leadership, which is essential for fostering a supportive and motivating atmosphere within the Ministry. This positive response serves as a strong foundation for further development and enhancement of Christian leadership practices in the organization, ultimately contributing to its overall effectiveness and mission fulfillment.

Variable (Y) Motivation Work

Based on the results of the distribution questionnaire about the Implementation of Christian Leadership In Motivation Work To Christian Religious Counselors at the Office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs of the Regency Kupang there are 39 respondents answered the questionnaire. They obtained results all processed data using the formula : $P = \frac{F}{N} \times 100\%$. The following is a summary table of the overall frequency of variable values (Y) as follows:

*Recapitulation Overall Frequency In Answer Items
Motivation Work (Y)*

Score (S)	Frequency (F)	(S) x (F)
5	221	1105
4	160	640
3	8	24
2	1	2
1	0	0
Amount	390	1771

From the table above, the known total score for variable Motivation Work (Y) is categorized based on the range ideal score where:

1. Maximum score obtained from 5 (Highest score) multiplied by the number of statement items times of respondents, namely $5 \times 10 \times 39 = 1950$
2. Amount minimum score obtained from 1 (Lowest score) multiplied by several question items times the respondents, namely $1 \times 10 \times 39 = 390$.

Range score = (Maximum score – Minimum score): 5. With this range score for variable Motivation Work (Y) = $(1950 - 390): 5 = 312$.

Based on the results of the research, 39 respondents scored variable Motivation Work (Y) of 1771, including category tall or If presented so calculated, namely : $= \frac{1771}{1950} \times 100\% = 90.82$ or 0.9082. If interpreted, the value of 0.90 or 90% is in the interval 0.80 - 1.00 or 86% - 100% with a very high level. So, the result of Work Motivation (Variable Y), which is 90.82, is very high.

Guidelines Interpretation

Coefficient Interval	Relationship Level
0.00 - 0.19	Very Low
0.20 - 0.39	Low
0.40 - 0.59	Currently
0.60 - 0.79	Tall
0.80 - 0.1.00	Very high

Based on the results of the calculations presented above, we can draw a clear conclusion regarding the findings from the questionnaire on work motivation. The calculated score for work motivation is 0.90, which falls within the interval of 0.80 to 1.00. According to established interpretative guidelines, this range is classified as "very high."

This indicates that the level of work motivation among the respondents is exceptionally strong. The high score of 0.90 reflects a significant degree of enthusiasm, commitment, and engagement among the Christian religious counselors regarding their work. Such a robust level of motivation suggests that the counselors are not only satisfied with their roles but are also likely to be highly effective in their duties.

Furthermore, the very high response rate to the work motivation questionnaire indicates a positive organizational climate and a supportive environment that fosters motivation. This outcome is crucial for the overall effectiveness of the Ministry's mission, as motivated counselors are better equipped to fulfill their responsibilities and contribute meaningfully to the spiritual and community needs of those they serve.

In summary, the findings underscore the importance of maintaining and enhancing factors that contribute to high work motivation among Christian religious counselors, as this will ultimately lead to improved performance and fulfillment of the Ministry's objectives. The overwhelmingly positive response to the work motivation questionnaire highlights the potential for continued growth and effectiveness within the organization.

5. Conclusion

Based on the research findings and discussions presented, we can draw several significant conclusions regarding the relationship between Christian leadership and work motivation among religious counselors. The analysis revealed that the variable representing the implementation of Christian leadership (Variable X) scored a high value of 0.90, indicating a robust correlation with work motivation. This suggests that effective implementation of Christian leadership principles plays a crucial role in enhancing the motivation of individuals within the organization.

Furthermore, the work motivation variable (Variable Y) also demonstrated a strong value of 0.90, underscoring the profound impact that motivated workers can have on the effectiveness of Christian leadership. This reciprocal relationship indicates that when Christian leadership is effectively implemented, it fosters a supportive environment that enhances the motivation of Christian religious counselors.

The results clearly illustrate that there is a significant and positive connection between Christian leadership and work motivation among the Christian religious counselors at the Ministry of Religion Office in Kupang Regency. The counselors expressed a very favorable response to the implementation of Christian leadership, highlighting its importance in their professional environment. This conclusion emphasizes the necessity of integrating Christian leadership principles into organizational practices to cultivate a motivated and engaged workforce, ultimately contributing to the overall effectiveness of the Ministry's mission.

In summary, the findings suggest that fostering strong Christian leadership is not only beneficial but essential for enhancing work motivation among counselors, creating a more dynamic and effective ministry.

Acknowledgments

The researchers express their sincere gratitude to all parties who have assisted in the preparation of this academic paper publication.

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